

I Analysis of motion direction consistency on the MOT17 and MOT20 datasets

Table 1. The analysis of the motion direction consistency of long-term occlusion targets in the training datasets of MOT17 and MOT20.

Δt	$\rho \leq 0.15$			$\rho \leq 0.25$		
	$\bar{\theta} < 0.5$	$\bar{\theta} < 1.0$	$\bar{\theta} > 1.0$	$\bar{\theta} < 0.5$	$\bar{\theta} < 1.0$	$\bar{\theta} > 1.0$
10	64%	78%	22%	64%	81%	19%
15	69%	82%	18%	68%	84%	16%
20	73%	85%	15%	72%	87%	13%
25	75%	87%	13%	75%	89%	11%
30	77%	88%	12%	78%	91%	9%

Since the MOT17 and MOT20 training datasets include labels with visibility scores, target position information, and temporal information, we can easily use this information to analyze the occlusion situation of different targets. We can calculate the angle difference between the target’s motion direction before entering a long-term occlusion period and its overall motion direction when it reappears. We only consider the angle difference in targets’ motion direction before and after long-term occlusion to test the consistency of target motion direction under long-term occlusion. We simulate the different occlusion scenarios using visibility scores and use ρ (visibility threshold) to determine if a target is in an occlusion state. For example, setting ρ to 0.15 means we consider the periods when the target’s visibility score is below 0.15 as occlusion periods. We use Δt as the long-term occlusion time threshold, which determines if the occlusion period satisfies the conditions for long-term occlusion. For instance, setting Δt to 10 means that we consider targets with occlusion periods exceeding 10 frames as long-term occluded targets.

As shown in Table 1, we analyzed the direction consistency of targets under long-term occlusion in the MOT17 and MOT20 training datasets based on the above method. The left half of Table 1 shows the direction consistency statistics when the ρ is set to 0.15, where $\bar{\theta}$ represents the average offset angle per frame. The right half of Table 1 shows the direction consistency statistics when the ρ is set to 0.25. We divide all targets in datasets into three ranges: $\bar{\theta} < 0.5$, $\bar{\theta} < 1.0$, and $\bar{\theta} > 1.0$. The values in Table 1 indicate the ratio of targets in different $\bar{\theta}$ ranges relative to the total number of targets in the dataset.

The results in Table 1 indicate that the motion direction of long-term occlusion targets is generally consistent during the occlusion period. The longer the occlusion period, the smaller the average motion direction offset, indicating stronger consistency in the targets’ motion direction. A higher visibility threshold also indirectly increases the length of the occlusion period, supporting our judgment about the direction consistency of long-term occlusion targets. The results in Table 1 can be analyzed that the motion direction of long-term occlusion targets is generally consistent, with small offset values, verifying our hypothesis in Section 3.1 of the paper.